

Prevalence and Pattern of Lung Dysfunction in Patients with Type 2 DM Attending a Tertiary Health Care Centre of Tripura by Spirometry

Dr. Saptadipa Das¹, Prof. Dr. Arindam Datta², Dr. Surajit Paul³

¹Resident Medical Officer, Dept. of Medicine, Tripura Medical College & BRAM Teaching hospital, Hapania

²Professor, Dept. of Medicine, Tripura Medical College & BRAM teaching hospital, Hapania

³Resident Medical Officer, Dept. of anaesthesiology, AGMC

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
22 February 2022

ABSTRACT

Introduction:- Diabetes has multiple microvascular and macrovascular complications, pulmonary complication though is less researched. In our present study we have tried to find out effects of diabetes mellitus on respiratory system.

Methods:- We did pulmonary function test on all patients admitted to Tripura medical college and Dr BRAM teaching hospital with diabetes mellitus after considering inclusion and exclusion criterias.

Result:- We have find higher prevalence of restricted lung disease in patients with diabetes mellitus and the relation between restrictive lung disease and HbA1C was statistically significant.

Corresponding Author:

Dr Surajit Paul

Conclusion:- So, should try to pick up lung disorders in diabetes patients from an early stage and try to treat it.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes mellitus, spirometry, restrictive lung function test.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus describes a metabolic disorder of multiple aetiology characterized by chronic hyperglycaemia with disturbances of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both.^{1,2,3,4} The presence of an extensive pulmonary microvascular circulation and abundant connective tissue raises the possibility that lung may also be a target organ in diabetes.^{5,6,7,8,9}

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This was an observational study done from February 2018 to august 2019 in Tripura medical college and Dr B.R. Ambedkar teaching hospital over 142 patients to study pulmonary function tests and its pattern in patients having diabetes mellitus.

RESULT

A total of 142 diagnosed patients with diabetes were included in the study.

97 patients (68.31%) of study population were having abnormal lung function whereas 45 patients (31.69%) were having normal lung function.

Male gender were having (62.9%) more abnormal lung function compared to female gender (37.1%) in this present study. But no statistical significant association was observed between lung function and gender.

Our study shows that participants with abnormal lung function had higher FBS (132 ± 33.8) compared to normal lung function (121 ± 27.3) and the difference was statistically significant (p value = 0.07). It also shows that participants with abnormal lung function have higher PPBS (182 ± 61.7) compared to normal lung function (176 ± 54.0) but the difference was not statistically significant (p value = 0.61). Our study shows significant reduction in FEV1 (65.8 ± 16.5) and FVC (68 ± 17) and increase in FEV1/FVC (93.7 ± 16.3).

Table 1:- Mean PFT values in study population

	FEV1	FVC	FEV1/FVC
MEAN	65.8	69.5	93.7
STANDARD DEVIATION	16.5	17.0	16.3

Mean FEV1 in our study population was 65.8 ± 16.5 and mean FVC was 69.5 ± 17 and mean FEV1/FVC was 93.7 ± 16.3 .

Our study demonstrates that there is restrictive pulmonary function pattern in diabetes type 2. Among 97 patients with

“Prevalence and Pattern of Lung Dysfunction in Patients with Type 2 DM Attending a Tertiary Health Care Centre of Tripura by Spirometry”

abnormal lung function, 15(15.5%) patients were having obstructive lung pattern and 82(84.5%) were having restrictive lung function pattern.

In our study we found that participants with abnormal lung function have higher duration (6.18 ± 4.61) of DM compared to normal lung function but the difference was not statistically significant (p value = 0.82).

Table 2: Distribution of study population based on duration of DM

	No lung abnormality	Obstructive	Restrictive	P value
Duration of DM	6 ± 3.32	5.33 ± 3.54	6.33 ± 4.79	0.68

Table 3: Distribution of study population based on HbA1c level

	Lung function		P value
	Normal	Abnormal	
HbA1c	5.80 ± 0.70	6.28 ± 1.11	0.01

The association between lung function and HbA1c value was statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

The present study showed patients with higher HbA1c were having higher abnormal function compared to patients with lower HbA1c. Participants with abnormal lung function have higher HbA1c (6.28 ± 1.11) compared to normal lung function (5.80 ± 0.70) and the difference was statistically significant (p value = 0.01).

The findings of present study thus reveals that the glycaemic exposure is a strong determinant of reduced pulmonary functions in type 2 diabetics. Thus, an intensive glycaemic management may reduce the pulmonary dysfunction to a great extent. This is in sync with multiple other studies that have found that there is high prevalence of abnormal lung function in diabetes patient.¹⁵⁻²⁵

CONCLUSION

It is advisable, therefore, that diabetic patients must undergo periodic spirometry tests to assess the severity of lung function impairment. Additional research is required to identify pathophysiologic mechanisms and to determine clinical significance of this association. In the meantime, clinicians should pay utmost attention to pulmonary functions in their patients with type 2 diabetes.

REFERENCES

1. Kasper et al 2017, Harrisons principles of internal medicine 20th edition vol 2, page 2286-2290

2. Guleria SSR, et al Pulmonary functions in patients with type-2 diabetic mellitus and correlation with anthropometry microvascular complications. Indian J Med Res 2004; 19: 6671.
3. World Health Organization. Diabetes: Fact sheet N 312, 2011. 4Aoril,2015.
4. Meo SA. Diabetes mellitus: health and wealth threat. Int J Diab Mellitus. 2009;1(1):42.
5. Marvisi M, et al. Pulmonary Function in non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. Respiration 2001; 68;268-72.
6. Ljubic s, et al Reduction of diffusion capacity for carbon monoxide in diabetic patients. Chest 1998; 114:1033-5
7. King H,et al Global burden of diabetes 1995-2025: prevalence numerical estimates and projections. Diabetes care 1998; 21:1414-31.
8. Benbassat Carlos A,et al Pulmonary function in patients with Diabetes Mellitus. The Am J Med Sci 2001; 322(3):127-132.
9. Sandler Malcom. Is the Lung a Target Organ in Diabetes Mellitus. Arch Intern Med.1990;150: 1385-1388.
10. Marvisi M, Lino Bartolini L, del Borrello P, Brianti M, Marrani G, Guariglia A, et al. Pulmonary Function in non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. Respiration 2001; 68;268-72. 3. James RG, Alberti KGMM, Mayer BD, Ralph AD, Allan D, Steven G, et al. Report on the expert committee on the diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. Diab Care. 2002;25:S5-20.
11. Sandler M. Is the lung a “target organ” in diabetes mellitus?. Arch Int Med. 1990;150(7):1385-8. 6. Sandler M, Bunn AE, Stewart RI. Cross-section study of pulmonary function in patients with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. Am Rev Respiratory Dis. 1987;135(1):223-9.
12. Hsia CC, Raskin P. Lung involvement in diabetes. Does it matter?. Diab Care. 2008;31:828-29. 8. Farina J, Furio V, Acenero FMJ, Muzas MA. Nodular fibrosis
13. Ruppel GL. Pulmonary function testing. trends and techniques. Respir Care Clin North Am. 1997;3:155-81.
14. McKay, Ray T, Horvath Edward. Pulmonary function testing in industry. In: Carl Zenz O, Dickerson Bruca, Horvath Edward P, editors. Occupational medicine. London: Mosby; 1984: 229.
15. Christine Jenkinsa. Spirometry performance in primary care: the problem, and possible solutions. Primary Care Respir J. 2009;18(3):128-9.
16. Meo SA, Al Drees AM, Arif M, Al-Rubean K. Lung function in type 2 Saudi diabetic patients. Saudi Med J. 2006;27(3):338-43.

“Prevalence and Pattern of Lung Dysfunction in Patients with Type 2 DM Attending a Tertiary Health Care Centre of Tripura by Spirometry”

17. Hsia CC. Recruitment of lung diffusing capacity: update of concept and application. *Chest*. 2002;122:1774-83.
18. Marvisi M, Lino Bartolini L, del Borrello P, Brianti M, Marrani G, Guariglia A, et al. Pulmonary Function in non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *Respiration*. 2001;68:268-78.
19. Ljubic s, Metelko z, car N, Roglic G, Drazic Z. Reduction of diffusion capacity for carbon monoxide in diabetic patients. *Chest* 1998; 114:1033-5
20. King H, Albert R, Herman W. Global burden of diabetes 1995-2025: prevalence numerical estimates and projections. *Diabetes care* 1998; 21:1414-31.
21. Benbassat Carlos A, Ervin Stern, Mordechai Kramer, Joseph Lebzelter, Ilana Blum, Gershon Fink. Pulmonary function in patients with Diabetes Mellitus. *The Am J Med Sci* 2001; 322(3):127-132.
22. Sandler Malcom. Is the Lung a Target Organ in Diabetes Mellitus. *Arch Intern Med*.1990;150: 1385-1388
23. Timothy J. Barriero, D.O., and Irene Perillo, M.D., University of Rochester School of Medicine and Dentistry, Rochester, New York) *Am Fam Physician*. 2004 Mar 1;69(5):1107-1115
24. Colp CR. Interpretation of pulmonary function tests. *Chest*. 1979;76:377-8.
25. Crapo RO. Pulmonary-function testing. *N Engl J Med*. 1994; 331:25-30.